

$\Delta S = \text{intercept} \times R$ (Table 2). The observed positive values of ΔS indicate the spontaneous formation of the complexes^{1,3}. The plots of $\log \beta$ against T^{-1} (Fig. 1) are straight lines which indicate that the values of ΔC_p are equal to zero^{1,6}.

Fig. 1. Plot of $\log \beta$ against T^{-1} for

- (1) $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{Sn}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CONC}_6\text{H}_4\text{O})_2$
- (2) $(n\text{-C}_4\text{H}_9)_2\text{Sn}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CONC}_6\text{H}_4\text{O})_2$
- (3) $(n\text{-C}_4\text{H}_9)_2\text{Sn}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CONC}_6\text{H}_4\text{O})_2$
- (4) $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{Sn}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CONC}_6\text{H}_4\text{CH}_3\text{O})_2$
- (5) $(n\text{-C}_4\text{H}_9)_2\text{Sn}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CONC}_6\text{H}_4\text{CH}_3\text{O})_2$
- (6) $(n\text{-C}_4\text{H}_9)_2\text{Sn}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CONC}_6\text{H}_4\text{CH}_3\text{O})_2$

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Solution Stabilities of Some Biligand Chelates of Copper(II), Nickel(II), Zinc(II) and Cadmium(II) with 1,10-Phenanthroline and Substituted Salicylic Acids

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LIKE 2,2'-bipyridine, 1,10-phenanthroline also forms stable complexes with metal ions at low pH which remain stable even at higher pH. Both have, therefore, been used widely as primary ligand in the study of a variety of mixed ligand complexes¹⁻⁷. Ternary complexes of the secondary ligands used in the present studies with a number of metal ions, using 2,2'-bipyridine as the primary ligand, have been reported^{6,7}. We report here the results of studies on mixed ligand chelates of copper(II), nickel(II), zinc(II) and cadmium(II) with 1,10-phenanthroline (primary ligand) and 4-hydroxy, 4-methyl and 3-methyl salicylic acids (secondary ligands) by pH metric method using a modified Irving and Rossotti technique⁸. Measurements were made at 25°, $\mu=0.1 M$ (NaNO_3) in 50% (v/v) aqueous ethanol.

The formation constants of the binary complexes of the secondary ligands have also been determined under similar conditions for a comparative study of both the types of the systems.

Experimental

Solutions of metal nitrates, sodium hydroxide, sodium nitrate and nitric acid were prepared in double distilled water and used after standardisation^{9,10}. Solutions of the ligands, phen, 4-HSA, 4-MSA and 3-MSA were prepared in redistilled ethanol by direct weighing. All chemicals were of analytical grade.

Measurements of pH were made with an expanded scale Elico pH meter (Model LI-15) with a glass-calomel electrode assembly at 25°. pH-Metric titrations were performed as described earlier^{6,7}. The final concentrations were $N^0 = 0.1 M$, $E^0 = 0.002 M$, $TC_L^0 = TC_M^0 = TC_{phen}^0 = 0.001 M$. All symbols have their usual meanings¹⁰. Figures of the titration curves are not shown here. The formation constants corresponding to proton ligand, binary M-L and ternary M-phen-L complexing systems were calculated as described earlier^{6,7}.

Results and Discussion

The protonation constants of the secondary ligands are presented in Table I. Formation curves of proton-secondary ligand systems are not shown here as they were given earlier^{6,7}. The basicity

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of the ligands follow the order 4-HSA > 4-MSA > 3-MSA.

TABLE 1—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF BINARY AND TERNARY CHELATES IN 50% (v/v) AQUEOUS ETHANOL temp. 25°; $\mu = 0.1M$

Cation	log K ₁	log K ₂	log K ₃	log K _{M.phen M.phen.L}
4-Hydroxy salicylic acid				
H ⁺	12.10	9.80	4.10	—
Cu ²⁺	9.60	—	—	9.75
Ni ²⁺	7.50	—	—	7.26
Zn ²⁺	7.63	—	—	7.36
Cd ²⁺	6.80	—	—	6.50
4-Methyl salicylic acid				
H ⁺	11.50	4.10	—	—
Cu ²⁺	8.90	—	—	9.05
Ni ²⁺	6.95	—	—	6.73
Zn ²⁺	7.30	—	—	7.16
Cd ²⁺	6.40	—	—	6.25
3-Methyl salicylic acid				
H ⁺	11.30	4.02	—	—
Cu ²⁺	8.15	—	—	8.42
Ni ²⁺	6.82	—	—	6.60
Zn ²⁺	7.04	—	—	6.90
Cd ²⁺	6.30	—	—	6.10

\bar{n} values of the binary and \bar{n} mix values of the ternary complexes extend over $\approx 0.0-1.0$ indicating the formation of 1:1 simple and mixed ligand chelates. The formation curves of only M-phen-3-MSA systems have been shown (Fig. 1) as illustration. Various stability constants evaluated are recorded in Table 1.

Fig. 1. Formation curves of M-phen-3-MSA systems.

It is interesting to note that the values of stoichiometric mixed ligand formation constant ($\log K_{M.phen.M.phen.L}^M$) are very close to 1:1 formation constant of metal secondary ligand ($\log K_{ML}^M$). From statistical considerations, values of $\log K_{M.phen.M.phen.L}^M$ should be appreciably less than $\log K_{ML}^M$ as the concentration of electrons around

(M.phen)²⁺ would be more than the same around (M.aq.)²⁺ owing to the greater coordinating tendency of phenanthroline than that of water. The reason being that two nitrogen atoms of the phenanthroline molecule form σ -bonds with the metal ion and in addition to this, there exists a strong tendency of M→N π -interaction due to the back donation of electrons from the metal d π -orbital to the vacant delocalized π -orbital over the phenanthroline molecule²¹. As a result of this back donation the concentration of electrons around the metal ion in (M.phen)²⁺ does not increase significantly due to which the electronegativity of the metal ion in this species remains almost the same as in (M.aq)²⁺ which in consequence justifies $\log K_{M.phen.M.phen.L}^M$

$$\approx \log K_{ML}^M$$

The stabilities of copper(II) complexes are usually higher than what could be expected from ionic radius or electronegativity considerations. This additional stability of copper(II) complexes may be attributed to the unique electronic configuration (d⁹) of Cu(II) ion which is capable of additional stabilization due to Jahn-Teller distortion. The stabilities of M-L and also M-phen.L chelates follow the order Ni(II) < Cu(II) > Zn(II) > Cd(II), which is in conformity with the Irving-William order. The Irving-William order runs roughly parallel to the second ionization potential of the elements which provides information on the affinity of the central atom to accept electrons from the ligands in bond formation. The stability order of a particular metal chelate with respect to secondary ligands is 4-HSA > 4-MSA > 3-MSA, which is also the order of basicity of the ligands. A plot of

Fig. 2. Plot of $\log K_{M.phen.M.phen.L}^M$ vs $\log K_{ML}^M$

$\log K_{M.phen.M.phen.L}^M$ vs $\log K_{ML}^M$ is linear indicating that the process of association of L with (M.phen)²⁺ species in the ternary complex follows in general the same pattern as that of the association of L with

(M.aq.)²⁺ species in the corresponding binary complexing systems. Further, the linear plot passes through the origin and the slope is unity showing that the values of $\log K_{ML}^M$ and those of corresponding $\log K_{M\text{phen.L}}^M$ are nearly equal irrespective of the nature of the secondary ligand^{1,2}. The probable structure of the simple and mixed ligand complexes of 3-MSA are given below.

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Determination of Formation Constants and Thermodynamic Parameters of Be(II) Complexes with Substituted Salicylic Acids

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KHADIKAR and coworkers have carried out extensive work on the complex formation of salicylic acid and substituted salicylic acids^{1,2}. In the present communication, studies on Be(II)

complexes with 5-chloro, 5-amino and 5-sulphosalicylic acids are reported. Bjerrum's method³ has been used to determine formation constants of the complexes. Stoichiometry has been determined conductometrically⁴ and by metal estimation. The formation constants have been determined at 30, 35 and 40 ± 0.1° and thermodynamic parameters ΔF , ΔH and ΔS are also reported. The bonding in the complexes is discussed on the basis of ir spectra.

Experimental

An expanded scale pH meter, Systronic Type 322, with an accuracy of ± 0.01 pH unit was used for pH measurements. All chemicals used were of B.D.H., AnalaR grade. Conductance measurements were made with a Philips conductivity bridge employing dip type conductivity cell. All measurements were carried out by using a thermostatic bath at 30, 35 and 40° with an accuracy of ± 0.1° at a constant ionic strength of 0.1 M (NaClO₄). The ir spectra of the isolated complexes and ligands used were recorded on a Perkin Elmer IR spectrophotometer, model 237 (4000-650 cm⁻¹) by KBr disc technique.

Results and Discussion

Application of monovariation method⁴ has clearly indicated the formation of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 (M : L) complexes of Be(II) with 5-chloro, 5-amino and 5-sulphosalicylic acids. The pH-metric titration of 1 : 1, 1 : 2 and 1 : 3 (M : L) mixtures show clear inflection at two, four and five equivalents of alkali indicating the formation of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes. The inflection at five equivalents of alkali for 1 : 3 titration curve is probably due to the presence of excess of ligand. Based on metal estimation of the isolated Be-complexes composition of different complexes is found to be Na₂Be(C₇H₃O₅Cl)₂·2H₂O (Found : Be, 1.87. Calcd. : Be, 2.09%); Na₂Be(C₇H₃O₅N)₂·2H₂O (Found : Be, 2.00. Calcd. : Be, 2.29%) and Na₂Be(C₇H₄O₆S)₂·2H₂O (Found : Be, 1.44. Calcd. : Be, 1.59%).

The values of \bar{n} and pL corresponding to different pH values have been calculated employing Bjerrum's pH titration technique. The formation curves were plotted and analysed to give the values of $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ as recorded in Table 1. The error limit in the values of $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ is found to be ± 0.01 and ± 0.02, respectively. A perusal of Table 1 shows that $\log K_1$ follows the order 5-ASA > 5-Cl.SA > 5-SSA, while $\log K_2$ values 5-Cl.SA > 5-ASA > 5-SSA.

The bigger difference between $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ and the high values of $\log K_1/K_2$ are because of steric hindrance of the linking of the second ligand molecule to small sized Be(II). The negative values of ΔH is a favourable requirement for a stable complex compound. The entropy changes calculated for above complexes have negative values.

The ir spectra of all the Be-complexes studied here show a marked shift in the >C=O stretching frequency of carboxylate group from ~ 1700 cm⁻¹ in ligand to about 1600 cm⁻¹ in complex. This observation provides the evidence of metal oxygen